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Chemical Investigation of the Roots of *Phyllanthus niruri*

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EARLIER communication¹ from this laboratory reported the isolation and characterization of two new glycoflavanones from the roots of *Phyllanthus niruri*. The plant is reputed for its medicinal importance.²

The air dried and powdered root of *P. niruri* was extracted with ethanol under reflux for 125 hr. The total ethanolic extract was kept in a refrigerator which deposited a white crystalline compound (0.92 g). Petroleum ether extract of the deposit gave a white amorphous mass (0.8 g) containing two compounds (TLC examination). These two compounds (designated as A and B) were separated over neutral alumina column, eluted with C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (6 : 4 v/v) and C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (2 : 8 v/v).

Compound-A, $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 211-12°, (α)_D²⁵ +27° (in $CHCl_3$) gave positive LB test for triterpenes. This was characterized as Lupa-20(29)-ene-3-β-01 by m.p., m.m.p., Co-IR and Co-TLC with an authentic sample of lupeol.

Compound-B, $C_{32}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 466), m.p. 213-14°, (α)_D²⁵ +50° (in $CHCl_3$) also gave a +Ve LB test for triterpenes. Alkaline hydrolysis of the compound-B gave an alcohol, identified as lupeol (Co-TLC and Co-IR)^{3,4} and CH_3COOH . Detailed study of the compound-B showed it to be the acetate of lupa-20(29)-ene-3-β-01 (confirmed by Co-TLC and Co-IR).

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Chemical Investigation of *Gerbera lanuginosa* Benth (whole plant) and Leaves of *Ipomoea fistulosa* Mart

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IPOMOEA fistulosa Mart (Convolvulaceae) is a South American plant migrated to India. Prolonged ingestion of this plant results in wasting, depression and other ill-defined pathology in sheep, cattle and goats.¹ From the leaves of the plant previous worker² reported the isolation of some fatty acid glycosides. Our present communication reports the isolation of β-sitosterol from the leaves of the same plant.

Dried and powdered leaves of the plant were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) for 10 hrs. The crude residue on chromatographic separation over silica-gel yielded a white crystalline solid, m.p. 133-137°, which on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine furnished the corresponding acetate, m.p. 128-130° (Lit³ m.p. 127-128°), identical (m.m.p., T.L.C., and I.R.) with an authentic specimen of β-sitosterol acetate. The benzene and ethylacetate extracts of the plant on chromatographic separation yielded no crystalline solid.

Gerbera lanuginosa Benth (Compositae) grows in the temperate Himalayas at the altitude of 4000-9500 ft. The white cotton like coating found under the surface of the leaves is used for staunching wounds and is also used for making coarse cloth⁴. Since no chemical investigation on this plant has so far been reported we were interested to undertake a systematic chemical examination of the plant.

Dried and powdered whole plant of *G. lanuginosa* was successively extracted with (A) petroleum ether (60-80°) and (B) benzene. The petroleum ether

extract was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction afforded no crystalline solid. The neutral fraction on chromatographic separation over silica-gel followed by crystallisation furnished two white crystalline solids, m.p. 285-287° and 265-267° respectively. These were identified as taraxeryl acetate⁵ and taraxerol⁶, (m.m.p., T.L.C. and I.R.) with authentic specimens of taraxeryl acetate and taraxerol respectively.

The benzene extract on chromatographic separation over silica-gel also furnished taraxeryl acetate⁵, m.p. 290-95°, identical (m.m.p. and T.L.C.) with an authentic specimen of taraxeryl acetate and taraxerol⁶, m.p. 270-76°, identical (m.m.p. and T.L.C.) with an authentic sample of taraxerol.

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Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Gardenia turgida* Roxb

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GARDENIA *turgida* Roxb (Rubiaceae) is a small spiny tree occurring throughout the greater part of India. Some parts of this plant have already been examined by different workers^{1,2}. The present communication embodies the chemical study on its roots and D-mannitol, gardenin A, gardenin B, gardenin E, oleanolic acid, α -amyrin and β -sitosterol have been isolated from the ethanolic extract.

The ethanol extract of the air dried roots was concentrated to 200 ml and kept in refrigerator, when a good amount of amorphous resinous matter

separated out. This was removed by decantation (Ethanol-insoluble fraction) and the mother liquor, fractionated into acidic and neutral sapogenins³. The neutral fraction was obtained in too small quantity to permit its isolation and identification.

Examination of Ethanol-insoluble Fraction :

The ethanol-insoluble portion was washed with hot benzene to remove waxy impurities and the resultant brown-yellow resinous mass was chromatographed over a column of deactivated alumina. Pure methanol furnished D-mannitol, m.p. 164-65°; hexacetyl, m.p. 120°; hexabenzooate, m.p. 147-48°; identical with authentic specimen.

Examination of Acidic Sapogenin Mixture :

The thick resinous acidic fraction on chromatography over silica gel gave following compounds :

Gardenin A—Light petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) yielded yellow needles, m.p. 163-64° (lit^{4,5} m.p. 164-65°); positive Wilson boric acid, Dimroth, Asahina and Inubuse and Shinoda tests; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm^{-1} 3350 (-OH stretch), 1660 (C=O stretch); PMR (CDCl_3); consistent with one reported by Seshadri *et al*⁴; acetate, m.p. 134-35° and methyl ether, m.p. 115°.

Gardenin B—Light petroleum-benzene (1 : 3) afforded fine needles, m.p. 177-78° (EtOH); M^+ 358. IR and NMR spectra were in concordance with those of an authentic sample⁶.

Gardenin E—Pure benzene eluted a compound as yellow needles, m.p. 230-31°; positive colour tests for 5-hydroxy flavones. Its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample as well as by Co-IR, PMR and mass spectra.

Oleanolic acid—Benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) afforded colourless needles, m.p. 305-6° (MeOH); ν_{\max} (Nujol) cm^{-1} 3200 (-OH stretch), 1710, 1680 (-CO stretch); acetate, m.p. 266-67° and methyl ester, m.p. 193-94°.

α -**Amyrin**—Benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) fraction was crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 183-84°. The identity was proved by Co-IR, Co-TLC, m.m.p. as well as by preparation of acetate, m.p. 222-23° and benzoate, m.p. 193°.

β -**Sitosterol**—The colourless flakes, m.p. 136-37° (MeOH) obtained from benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 3) were directly compared with an authentic sample.

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